

Automated Detection and Counting of Benthic Taxa using Computer Vision on ROV Videos

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Abstract

Developing robust and cost-effective methods for benthic biodiversity assessments is crucial for mapping vulnerable habitats and designing effective management strategies. Achieving this objective requires increasing the spatial and temporal coverage of observations and optimizing the cost-effectiveness of sampling efforts. Remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) together with computer vision-based tools present great potential for cost-effectively mapping benthic taxa. However, the processing of hours of footage manually is time-consuming, making the process inefficient and costly. To address this challenge, an automated system for the detection and abundance estimation of 13 key benthic taxa was developed. The proposed approach analyses videos obtained with a ROV and provides taxon-specific counts to support habitat monitoring. It was developed and tested using a total of 42 sampling transects, resulting in approximately 20 hours of high-quality video footage. Two models were trained and compared for benthic taxa detection: YOLOv8x and Faster R-CNN. Their performance was evaluated using mAP50, reaching values of 0.782 ± 0.027 for YOLOv8x and 0.755 ± 0.032 for Faster R-CNN, indicating strong detection capability by both models. Since YOLOv8x showed a slightly higher performance with lower variance, it was selected and used for abundance estimation. Comparison of automated abundance estimates with manual counts across 10 transects gave a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 20.4%, indicating a relatively high level of agreement between automated and expert-based estimations. Consequently, this approach enables non-invasive and cost-effective monitoring of benthic biodiversity through digital imagery while extending detection to taxa not previously considered, offering valuable insights for benthic habitat preservation.

Keywords:

Computer vision, biodiversity monitoring, underwater video surveys, benthic mapping, marine imaging

33 1 Introduction

34 Monitoring benthic biodiversity is critical for understanding how ecosystems respond to
35 human pressures and climate change. However, obtaining meaningful insights into
36 biodiversity and its dynamics requires expanding the spatial and temporal coverage of
37 observations, harmonizing sampling methods, and improving the coordination of
38 sampling efforts (Chust et al., 2022; Muller-Karger et al., 2018; Valdez et al., 2023).
39 Enhancing our ability to automate data collection and processing can significantly
40 increase both the quantity and quality of information available to scientists and decision-
41 makers (Irigoien et al., 2009; Jetz et al., 2019). However, the large volume of data makes
42 extracting valuable information a time-consuming and challenging task. Therefore,
43 developing cost-effective biodiversity monitoring tools is crucial for identifying and
44 mapping vulnerable habitats and establishing management strategies that safeguard high-
45 value ecosystem services. These efforts also support the evaluation of progress toward
46 international commitments, including the UN Sustainable Development Goals, the
47 Convention on Biological Diversity Targets, and the EU Biodiversity Strategy, while
48 underpinning evidence-based conservation and management actions (Palomares et al.,
49 2021; Vinuesa et al., 2020).

50 Several methods are available for monitoring benthic biodiversity, ranging from
51 traditional physical sampling techniques, such as grabs, corers, trawls, and dredges
52 (Eleftheriou, 2013), to more recent technologies like acoustic mapping (Mooney et al.,
53 2020), environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding (Pawlowski et al., 2022), aerial
54 photography and satellite imagery (C. Zhang et al., 2013), and underwater digital imaging
55 platforms such as autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) (Piechaud et al., 2019),
56 remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) (Tait et al., 2023), towed video systems (Liu & Wang,
57 2021; Prado et al., 2019), and baited remote underwater video stations (BRUVs) (Devine
58 et al., 2019; Ghazilou et al., 2016). This study focuses on the automatic mapping of
59 benthic species using underwater digital images acquired by ROVs. When combined with
60 computer vision (CV) techniques, underwater imagery offers substantial advantages for
61 benthic species monitoring, facilitating automated counting and enabling future
62 estimations of species density.

63 Recent advances in AI-driven digital imaging, particularly deep learning models, present
64 significant potential for achieving more accurate and cost-effective mapping of benthic
65 species (Rubbens et al., 2023). Over the past decades, the field of CV has evolved rapidly
66 from more traditional features extraction methods (Schoening et al., 2012; Seiler et al.,
67 2012) to deep learning (DL) approaches that are delivering state-of-the-art results across
68 a wide range of visual recognition tasks. Traditional CV models work by extracting
69 predefined visual features from images and using classical machine learning algorithms
70 to recognize patterns on these features. Modern DL methods, particularly convolutional
71 neural networks (CNNs), automatically learn hierarchical features directly from raw
72 images. Accordingly, DL offers key advantages, such as automatic feature extraction,
73 high accuracy in complex recognition tasks, scalability across diverse datasets, and

74 robustness to variations in image quality, making it ideal for challenging environments
75 like underwater monitoring (Rubbens et al., 2023).

76 Analysing underwater imagery presents unique technical challenges, including
77 inconsistent object appearance across frames, low light conditions, frequent occlusions,
78 complex and heterogeneous backgrounds, water turbidity, and image noise. In addition,
79 colour attenuation and light scattering in the water column often degrade image quality
80 and alter the visual characteristics of benthic organisms, making their identification
81 particularly difficult. Despite these challenges, several automatic methods have been
82 proposed for benthic species monitoring (Devine et al., 2019; Ghazilou et al., 2016; Iyer
83 et al., 2024; Piechaud et al., 2019; Trotter et al., 2025; C. Zhang et al., 2013). While these
84 methods have shown promising results, their generalisation capability remains limited,
85 particularly when applied to new environments or unseen taxa (Csurka, 2017). One of the
86 main persistent constraints is the availability of high-quality annotated datasets tailored
87 to specific regions and target taxa, as annotation is time-consuming and requires expert
88 knowledge.

89 To address this monitoring challenge, this study develops an automatic CV method to
90 detect and estimate the abundance of 13 benthic taxa using video footage collected by a
91 ROV across multiple transects in the southeastern region of the Bay of Biscay. The main
92 objective is to establish an automated or semi-automatic tool that can reduce the time
93 required for benthic biodiversity monitoring compared to conventional current
94 approaches (i.e., manual detection and counting). Moreover, to the best of our knowledge,
95 this is the first time that several of these taxa have been modelled using such approaches.
96 Therefore, this work contributes to the advancement of reliable AI-based tools for
97 biodiversity monitoring, offering a more efficient benthic mapping and supporting their
98 integration into marine ecological research and managementp'0

99 **2 Material and methods**

100 The methodology for developing and validating the models followed a sequential
101 workflow, as illustrated in Figure 1. This workflow comprises five main stages: data
102 collection, video annotation, preprocessing of the resulting dataset, model training, and
103 final model testing to identify the best-performing configuration. The following sections
104 describe each step in detail.

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Figure 1. Pipeline used to train, validate, and test the computer vision model, including data collection, preprocessing, hyperparameter optimization, and performance evaluation. Note that mAP50 is the mean average precision using an intersection over union (IoU) thresholds value of 0.5, while MAPE is the mean absolute percentage error.

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2.1 Study area and data collection

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The study area is located in the Basque continental shelf in the south-eastern coast of the Bay of Biscay (Figure 2). As a biogeographic transition zone between subtropical and boreal regions, the Bay of Biscay hosts a wide and diverse number of marine organisms (Borja et al., 2019). In addition, it hosts important habitats and biodiversity spots such as seamounts and canyons (Galparsoro et al., 2012, 2015, 2019). Hard substrate related habitats cover approximately 50% of the continental shelf, while the remaining area is dominated by sedimentary habitats, primarily composed of sand and mud (Galparsoro et al., 2015). These two main habitats can be further divided, as proposed by Galparsoro et al., (2015) into four classes for hard substrates and nine for the soft substrates. Moreover, the area is subject to intense fishing activity along the surveyed transects, including bottom-trawling (Fernandes et al., 2019).

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122 Onboard the Minibex ship, a SUPER-ACHILLE ROV, operated via a Tether

Figure 2. The Bay of Biscay, showing the study area and transects.

123 Management System, was used for image collection. The ROV was equipped with a
 124 transponder providing georeferenced positioning data and a dual-camera system (full HD
 125 and 4K), allowing high-resolution video acquisition and real-time monitoring. During the
 126 surveys, the ROV maintained a constant speed of approximately 0.7 knots along
 127 predetermined transects. During the sampling campaign carried out in June 2023, 42
 128 transects were conducted across a broad depth range of 74 to 670 meters (Figure 2).
 129 Individual deployments lasted between 16 and 53 minutes, covering linear distances
 130 between 234 and 474 meters. This resulted in the collection of a total of 20 hours of high-
 131 quality video footage. The videos obtained are representative of two main types of benthic
 132 habitats (rocky and sedimentary substrates), covering areas subject to different levels of
 133 fishing intensity. Figure 3 shows representative frames from the ROV footage, illustrating
 134 a gradient from rocky to sedimentary habitats.

135 Figure 3. Representative frames recorded by the ROV, showing typical underwater scenes encountered during the
 136 survey.

137 2.2 Video annotation

138 Videos captured by the ROV were converted into still frames at a rate of one image every
 139 two seconds for subsequent expert video annotation. These frames were then annotated
 140 using the open-source Computer Vision Annotation Tool (CVAT) developed by Intel
 141 (2018). This tool allows for the creation, storage and extraction of manually annotated
 142 information. To facilitate and accelerate experts' annotation process, the frames were
 143 annotated using a semi-automatic approach (Figure 1). The first five tracks were manually
 144 annotated to create an initial dataset to train a CV model that subsequently assisted in
 145 labelling the remaining videos. Afterwards, every two to three newly annotated videos,
 146 the model was retrained, and this iterative process continued until all the videos were
 147 annotated. The based model used was YOLOv8x, specifically the Megalodon detector
 148 developed by the Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute (MBARI) using publicly
 149 available FathomNet data (MBARI, 2025).

150 The final annotated dataset comprised 13 benthic taxa (Figure 4), encompassing taxa
 151 associated with both sedimentary and rocky substrates. These taxa were selected because
 152 they are characteristic of the study area, readily identifiable owing to their conspicuous
 153 size, distinct coloration, and recognisable shape. Eight taxa were selected for sedimentary
 154 substrates (*Leptometra celtica*, *Funiculina quadrangularis*, *Ophiura ophiura*,
 155 *Gracilechinus acutus*, *Parastichopus regalis*, *Ophiothrix fragilis*, Pennatulidae, and
 156 *Alcyonium palmatum*), while *Dendrophyllia cornigera*, Gorgoniidae, *Geodia* spp.,
 157 Sponges (porifera), and *Phakellia ventilabrum* were selected for rocky substrates.

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159 **Figure 4.** List of target taxa and sample images obtained from the surveyed transects.

160 **2.3 Data splitting and cross-validation**

161 In order to prevent overfitting caused by temporal correlation between consecutive
162 frames, each video track was divided into ten non-overlapping segments. This strategy
163 reduces the probability that adjacent and highly similar frames from the same sequence
164 are distributed across different data subsets, thereby limiting bias in model evaluation.
165 Model development followed a stratified 10-fold cross-validation scheme, which was
166 consistently applied to the entire processing pipeline to obtain robust performance
167 estimates (Fernandes-Salvador et al., 2026).

168 However, in multi-label classification problems, achieving an exact match of taxa
169 distributions across subsets is challenging due to the large number of possible label
170 combinations (labelsets). Traditional stratified sampling becomes impractical when some
171 labelsets are represented by only a single instance (Sechidis et al., 2011). To address this
172 limitation, a relaxed random stratified splitting strategy was adopted, aiming to preserve
173 the original distribution of each individual label within each subset as closely as possible.
174 Finally, the data were split into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) subsets.

175 **2.4 Data preprocessing**

176 In the first step, the data were standardized by normalizing pixel values and resizing all
177 images to a uniform resolution. Moreover, background images (i.e., negative samples that
178 did not contain target taxa) were added to the dataset to reduce false positives (FP). These
179 background samples were selected during the semi-automated labelling process by adding
180 as background frames those that exclusively contained false positives. Then, to mitigate
181 class imbalance, a data augmentation strategy based on image-level oversampling was
182 applied to increase the representation of minority classes. Each image was temporarily
183 assigned a representative label corresponding to the most frequent taxon among its
184 annotations. These representative labels were used solely to guide a random oversampling
185 procedure, whereby images associated with underrepresented classes were sampled more
186 frequently. Although this approach does not result in a perfectly balanced dataset, it

187 effectively reduces class imbalance while preserving the original multi-label structure.
188 Data augmentation was applied exclusively to the training subset.

189 **2.5 Model training**

190 **2.5.1 Proposed multi-object tracking and counting method**

191 The proposed approach consists of three main components: i) an object detection model;
192 ii) a multi-object tracking algorithm; and iii) a counting strategy.

193 For object detection, two computer vision models were evaluated: YOLOv8x (Jocher et al., 2023) and Faster R-CNN (Ren et al., 2016). YOLOv8x is a one-stage detector
194 optimized for real-time applications due to its high inference speed, whereas Faster R-
195 CNN is a two-stage detector that prioritizes accuracy, at the expense of increased
196 computational complexity and longer inference times. Both models have been extensively
197 used in the literature for a wide range of applications, including species detection (Huang
198 et al., 2019; S. Li et al., 2022; Liu & Wang, 2021), fish detection and counting
199 (Kandimalla et al., 2022; Z. Zhang et al., 2024), and mapping vulnerable areas (Abad-
200 Uribarren et al., 2022).
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202 Once the models are trained, object tracking becomes essential for the continuous
203 identification and monitoring of target taxa across consecutive video frames. This study
204 employs the BoT-SORT algorithm, introduced by Aharon et al. (2022). BoT-SORT
205 builds upon the widely used SORT (Simple Online and Realtime Tracking) framework
206 by incorporating appearance-based re-identification features and enhanced motion
207 modelling. These improvements make it particularly effective in challenging underwater
208 environments characterized by occlusions, overlapping objects, and variable lighting
209 conditions.

210 For the counting strategy, detection and tracking are applied to every frame of the video
211 sequence. The final object count is obtained by enumerating the unique track IDs assigned
212 to each individual throughout the sequence, ensuring that each entity is counted only once.

213 **2.5.2 Training approach**

214 The YOLOv8x model was trained using the Ultralytics library (Ultralytics, 2023), with
215 the pretrained FathomNet Megalodon Detector (MBARI, 2025) serving as the base
216 model. This model was trained on the complete FathomNet database (Katija et al., 2022)
217 and fine-tuned to detect a single class. For the Faster R-CNN model, the implementation
218 was conducted using the PyTorch framework, employing a pretrained ResNet-50-FPN
219 backbone model (Y. Li et al., 2021) trained on the COCO dataset (Lin et al., 2014). Both
220 algorithms were trained following a transfer learning approach, which consists of
221 retraining models originally developed for a specific task to different but related tasks.
222 This strategy significantly reduces the need for large datasets and computational
223 resources.

224 The experiments were conducted on a workstation running Ubuntu 20.04 and Python
225 3.12.7. The deep learning models were implemented in PyTorch 2.7.0 and executed using

226 CUDA 12.4. All computations were carried out on an NVIDIA Tesla V100-PCIE-16GB.
227 The training parameter used are shown in Table 1, and for those parameters not described,
228 default values provided by the respective frameworks were applied. Although the two
229 models differ in the number of parameters, the selected configuration aimed to ensure a
230 fair and consistent comparison within the scope of this study.

231 *Table 1. Training hyperparameters used for the YOLOv8x and Faster R-CNN models.*

Parameter	YOLOv8x	Faster R-CNN
Epoch	200	200
Patience	20	20
Image size	1920x1080	1920x1080
Optimizer	SDG	SDG
Learning rate	0.01	0.005
Momentum	0.937	0.9
Weight decay	0.0005	0.0005

232 The BoT-SORT algorithm was configured with specific parameters to enhance tracking
233 accuracy. The tracker employed a primary association threshold of 0.7 and a secondary
234 threshold of 0.2. New tracks were initiated when detections exceeded a confidence
235 threshold of 0.3. A track buffer of 120 frames was set to define the lifespan of inactive
236 tracks. Matching between detections and existing tracks was governed by an Intersection
237 over Union (IoU) based threshold of 0.75, with confidence scores integrated with spatial
238 distance metrics to improve matching robustness. Global motion compensation was
239 enabled using the sparseOptFlow method. All parameters were previously calibrated to
240 ensure optimal performance under the operational conditions.

241 **2.6 Model evaluation metrics**

242 Evaluating CV models for quantifying the abundance of benthic taxa requires the use of
243 key performance metrics to ensure accuracy, reliability, and generalizability. The
244 selection of metrics depends on the specific tasks, such as classification, detection,
245 segmentation, tracking, or counting. Since the goal of this study was to detect and count
246 several benthic taxa to support future density estimations per surveyed linear meter,
247 models were evaluated using metrics that assess performance in two areas: (i) object
248 detection and (ii) abundance counting.

249 **Object detection** tasks are evaluated using metrics that measure their accuracy to identify
250 and localize objects within images. In this study, model performance was assessed based
251 on mean average precision (mAP), a metric that balances precision and recall across
252 multiple Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds. This approach provides a
253 comprehensive evaluation of the model's ability to correctly detect and localize objects.

254 The mathematical expression of the considered metric is the following:

$$mAP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n AP_k \quad (1)$$

255 where n is the total number of classes being evaluated and AP is the average precision of
 256 the i -th class, and it is calculated as follows:

$$AP = \int_0^1 P(r) dr \quad (2)$$

257 where P represents the precision of this class, and r denotes the recall of this class.

258 **Object counting** is the main aim of the proposed methods as the goal is to estimate the
 259 abundance of the target taxa. Common metric used in counting is the mean absolute
 260 percentage error (MAPE).

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{K_t - T_i}{K_t} \right| \quad (3)$$

261 where T_t represents the number of predicted objects in the t th test video, while K_t denotes
 262 the true number of objects at t -th test video.

263 The overall model testing and selection framework is shown in Figure 1, where final
 264 models (i.e., not the intermediate models used to assist in video labelling) were evaluated
 265 using a 10-cross validation approach. To select the best-performing model, the mAP_{50}
 266 was used, which quantifies detection accuracy based on a 0.5 intersection-over-union
 267 (IoU) threshold.

268 **3 Results**

269 **3.1 Annotation results**

270 A total of 10373 images were annotated, and the number of instances per class is
 271 presented in Figure 5. The class distribution reveals a pronounced imbalance, with a small
 272 number of taxa accounting for a large proportion of the total annotations. Such imbalance
 273 can adversely affect model training by biasing predictions towards dominant classes. For
 274 this reason, class imbalance was addressed during the data preprocessing stage, as
 275 described in Section 2.3. The taxa are coloured according to their typical habitat,
 276 illustrating that rocky-habitat taxa dominate in terms of the number of individual
 277 annotations compared with sediment-associated taxa.

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Figure 5. Distribution of instances across classes in the dataset.

280 3.2 Models' detection results and analysis

281 This section details the models' ability to detect the target taxa in each frame, with their
 282 detection performance presented in Table 2. The mAP50 values correspond to the average
 283 across 10 splits using a relaxed random stratified 10-fold cross validation strategy.
 284 Overall, YOLOv8x achieved a slightly higher mean mAP50 (0.782 ± 0.027) compared to
 285 Faster R-CNN (0.755 ± 0.032), indicating a minor advantage in detection accuracy. The
 286 variability in the corresponding standard deviations also highlights slight differences in
 287 model stability, showing consistent prediction by both models. A paired t-test on
 288 fold-wise mean scores showed that YOLO significantly outperformed Faster R-CNN
 289 (mean difference = 0.0268, $p = 0.009$).

290 **Table 2.** Performance comparison, in terms of mean and standard deviation (sd), between
 291 YOLOv8x and Faster R-CNN based on mAP50 values. The best result for each model is
 292 highlighted in bold.

Class	mAP50			
	YOLOv8x		Faster R-CNN	
	mean	sd	mean	sd
<i>D. cornigera</i>	0.897	0.018	0.816	0.111
<i>L. celtica</i>	0.924	0.041	0.844	0.029
<i>P. regalis</i>	0.811	0.076	0.919	0.034
<i>G. acutus</i>	0.758	0.184	0.794	0.089
<i>O. ophiura</i>	0.824	0.085	0.663	0.190
<i>O. fragilis</i>	0.727	0.124	0.873	0.046
Gorgoniidae	0.868	0.055	0.725	0.163
<i>F. quadrangularis</i>	0.668	0.168	0.819	0.063

Sponge	0.774	0.038	0.774	0.156
<i>P. ventilabrum</i>	0.828	0.028	0.732	0.047
<i>Geodia</i> spp.	0.415	0.107	0.323	0.117
<i>A. palmatum</i>	0.783	0.160	0.767	0.022
Pennatulidae	0.882	0.081	0.763	0.236
Mean	0.782	0.027	0.755	0.032

293 When analysing performance across classes, both YOLOv8x and Faster R-CNN achieved
 294 satisfactory detection results across most classes. However, performance varied
 295 considerably among classes, although the majority exhibited mAP50 values over 0.66.
 296 YOLOv8x outperformed Faster R-CNN in several classes (8 out of 13), such as for *L.*
 297 *celtica* (0.924 vs. 0.844) and *D. cornigera* (0.897 vs. 0.816). Conversely, Faster R-CNN
 298 achieved better results for *P. regalis* (0.919 vs. 0.811) and *O. fragilis* (0.873 vs. 0.727).
 299 The only exception is *Geodia* spp., for which both models performed poorly (Table 2).
 300 This low accuracy is likely due to the high visual similarity between *Geodia* spp. and
 301 other sponges, as *Geodia* spp. itself belongs to the sponge family. Therefore, the results
 302 indicate that YOLOv8x exhibits superior suitability for detecting benthic taxa,
 303 consequently, it was selected for subsequent abundance estimation analysis.

304 3.3 Models counting results and analysis

305 To assess the YOLOv8x ability to estimate the abundance of each target taxa, 10 videos
 306 from tracks not previously used during training were employed. The counting procedure
 307 was applied across entire transects, representing a substantial challenge to test the
 308 generalizability and robustness of the object detection model and tracking algorithm. For
 309 validation, the total number of individuals present in each transect was manually
 310 annotated by experts using two-second intervals throughout the entire video. These
 311 manual counts were treated as ground truth for assessing the accuracy of the automated
 312 pipeline.

313 Table 3 presents the comparison between the manual counting by experts and the model
 314 estimated abundances. The selected transects for validation cover a wide range of taxa
 315 densities, which range from only 53 to more than 12,600 individuals. This variability is
 316 primarily driven by substrate type, with sedimentary habitats showing the fewest
 317 individuals (H-J), rocky substrates (A-E) having the highest abundances and mixed areas
 318 displaying intermediate values (F-G). Including this range of habitat types is essential for
 319 evaluating model performance under different conditions, since each taxa tends to be
 320 associated with particular substrate characteristics.

321 **Table 3.** Comparison between actual abundances and model-estimated abundances. MAPE is the mean absolute
 322 percentage error.

Track	Manual abundances	YOLOv8x		MAPE (%)
		Total	Diff. (%)	
A	12635	11744	-7.0	9.9
B	6713	5864	-12.6	
C	3036	2429	-20.0	

Taxa	Manual	YOLOv8x	MAPE (%)
D	2698	2559	-5.1
E	2664	2687	0.9
F	1273	901	-29.2
G	1271	1256	-1.2
H	302	415	37.4
I	117	161	37.6
J	53	81	52.8
Total	30762	28097	-8.7

323 In rocky habitats (tracks A-E), the model underestimates abundances with a MAPE of
324 9.9%, which is relatively moderate considering the high densities of these transects
325 (>2,500 individuals). In mixed habitats (tracks F and G), the model also underestimates
326 abundances, with a higher mean error (MAPE of 15.2%); however, this error remains
327 reasonable considering the complexity of the task. Contrarily, in sedimentary substrates
328 (tracks H-J), the model overestimates abundances by 42.6%, indicating a large error in
329 automatic counting. This high error observed in low-density transects likely reflects the
330 strong sensitivity of percentage-based error metrics to false positives, where even a small
331 number of incorrect detections can disproportionately inflate the overall error.

332 In addition, Table 4 details the model's performance at taxa level by comparing the total
333 number of individuals detected by YOLOv8x with the manual counts. For the most
334 abundant classes, the agreement with manual annotations was relatively good (MAPE <
335 15%). These taxa account for almost 96% of all the individuals (i.e., *D. cornigera*, *P.*
336 *ventilabrum*, Sponges, and *L. celtica*), demonstrating to be a good approach to obtain a
337 global estimation across all transects.

338 In contrast, several taxa exhibited greater discrepancies between manual and automated
339 counts. Particularly noteworthy is the underestimation of *Geodia* spp. by 55.3%, missing
340 255 individuals, and the overestimation of *F. quadrangularis* by 66.1%. In the case of
341 *Geodia* spp., this underestimation is consistent with the model's limited detection
342 capacity (mPA50 of 0.415). Among the less abundant taxa, *P. regalis* (-49.2%) and *E.*
343 *acutus* (-34.1%) were also underestimated by the model, while *Pennatulidae*, *A.*
344 *palmatum*, and *O. ophiura* were overestimated. A particular case is *O. fragilis*, for which
345 YOLOv8x failed to detect any individuals, despite 25 individuals being recorded
346 manually (100% error).

347 **Table 4.** Comparison at taxa level between manual counting and YOLOv8x.

Taxa	Manual abundances	YOLOv8x	MAPE (%)
<i>D. cornigera</i>	18779	17518	-6.7
<i>P. ventilabrum</i>	4009	3444	-14.1
Sponge	3800	3246	-14.6
<i>L. celtica</i>	2945	2854	-3.1
Gorgoniidae	429	343	-20.0
<i>Geodia</i> spp.	407	182	-55.3

Taxa	Manual abundances	YOLOv8x	MAPE (%)
<i>F. quadrangularis</i>	233	387	66.1
<i>P. regalis</i>	59	30	-49.2
<i>E. acutus</i>	41	27	-34.1
<i>O. fragilis</i>	25	0	-100
Pennatulidae	16	25	56.3
<i>A. palmatum</i>	13	20	53.8
<i>O. ophiura</i>	6	21	250.0
Total	30762	28097	55.6%

348 When aggregating all taxa, the total abundance estimated by YOLOv8x (28,097
349 individuals) was close to that of the manual counting (30,762 individuals), but the overall
350 mean absolute percentage error across taxa was still relatively high (MAPE = 55.6%).
351 This indicates that, although the model can approximate overall abundance at the
352 community level, caution is required when interpreting taxa specific abundance estimates,
353 especially for rare or morphologically complex taxa.

354 4 Discussion

355 Annotation quality constitutes a critical source of uncertainty, especially when attempting
356 to quantify taxa separately from their broader taxonomic groups (e.g., *Geodia* spp. vs
357 other sponges) or when annotating species that form colonies (i.e., *D. cornigera*).
358 Previous studies have shown detection success rates of around 80% and classification
359 accuracies between 84–95% for human observers (Culverhouse et al., 2003; Durden et
360 al., 2016). Self-consistency and inter-observer consensus are also low (84-44% and 57-
361 35%, respectively), implying that manual annotations introduce substantial variability
362 into ground-truth data (Beijbom et al., 2015; Culverhouse et al., 2003; Lekunberri et al.,
363 2025). In addition to these uncertainties, manual annotation is inherently time-consuming
364 and resource-intensive, often requiring expert knowledge and substantial effort to process
365 large volumes of imagery. In this context, the iterative methodology proposed in this
366 study aims to mitigate these limitations by progressively refining annotations and model
367 performance, thereby reducing annotation effort while maintaining data quality and
368 improving overall efficiency. Consequently, model evaluation metrics should be
369 interpreted with caution, as they remain intrinsically linked to the quality and consistency
370 of the annotations.

371 In the literature, few studies have addressed detection of similar target benthic taxa using
372 computer vision models. Iyer et al., (2024) trained a YOLOv8 model to detect several
373 classes, including Ophiuroidea, the group to which the *O. ophiura* belongs, achieving a
374 mAP50 of 0.61. In Abad-Uribarren et al., (2022), several architectures to detect *D.*
375 *cornigera* were evaluated, with FasterRCNN+Resnet101 achieving the highest precision
376 (0.86). Prado et al., (2020) reported precision values of 0.59 for *P. ventilabrum* and 0.69
377 for *D. cornigera* using YOLOv4. Gayá-Vilar et al., (2024) tested multiple architectures
378 across two study areas, reporting precision ranges of 0.717–0.914 for *P. ventilabrum* and
379 0.650–0.925 for *D. cornigera*. Overall, the performance of our models is comparable or

380 even superior to that reported in previous studies, despite being trained on a larger number
381 of classes and an imbalanced dataset. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first
382 to address the detection and classification of ten taxa that have not previously been studied
383 in the literature.

384 When comparing our model performance metrics with broader studies on other benthic
385 taxa, the reported mPA for their detector models ranged from 0.45 to 0.84 (Iyer et al.,
386 2024; McEver et al., 2023; Piechaud et al., 2019; Trotter et al., 2025). These studies differ
387 widely in the number of classes (7–52) and in the morphological diversity of the
388 organisms considered. The number of classes is a critical factor, as increasing class
389 diversity often reduces model accuracy. For instance, (Piechaud et al., 2019) observed a
390 decline in precision from 0.69 to 0.32 when the number of classes increased from 7 to 27.
391 This can be illustrated by two studies whose detectors achieved precision values of 0.912
392 and 0.860 for *Syringamina fragilissima* and *D. cornigera* (Abad-Uribarren et al., 2022;
393 Piechaud & Howell, 2022). Note that, in this study YOLO reached a mAP50 of 0.897 for
394 *D. cornigera*, slightly outperforming previous results.

395 The only taxa with low detection ability was *Geodia* spp. (<0.65), likely due to the
396 difficulty of discriminating *Geodias* pp. from other sponges, which complicates
397 annotation even for experts. In this case, inter-class variability is minimal, making reliable
398 differentiation challenging during the labelling process. This limitation highlights the
399 need for more refined classification strategies or additional discriminative features to
400 improve the detection of morphologically similar taxa. Additional factors, such as
401 inconsistent labelling or ambiguous morphological boundaries, may further contribute to
402 these errors.

403 Regarding taxa counting, the model tends to underestimate abundances in transects with
404 high-density of individuals (i.e., rocky substrates) and to overestimate them in transects
405 with low-density of individuals (i.e., sedimentary substrates). A noteworthy case is *O.*
406 *fragilis*, for which no individuals were detected by YOLOv8x despite 25 individuals
407 recorded manually (100% error). This discrepancy may be explained by the fact that 17
408 of the 25 individuals come from a single transect where *O. fragilis* occurred on top of a
409 *F. quadrangularis* (Figure 6) This association was not present in any other training
410 example, which likely explains the observed mismatch. Consequently, the current model
411 version should be applied with caution or under human supervision especially when
412 analysing sedimentary habitats.

413 Figure 6. Example of *O. fragilis* not counted due to co-occurrence with *F. quadrangularis*.

414 Finally, the outputs generated by the proposed approach can be used to estimate a wide
 415 range of indicators relevant for assessing the status of benthic habitats and impacts of
 416 human activities. These indicators span from community metrics, such as density,
 417 biomass, and diversity to more integrative indices capable of evaluating the impacts of
 418 human activities, including trait-based indices (Hinz et al., 2021). In addition, the
 419 spatially explicit information produced by the proposed approach can support
 420 ecosystem-based marine spatial planning (EB-MSP), whose objective is to analyse and
 421 manage the spatial distribution of human uses to maintain existing and emerging
 422 activities, minimise conflicts, and safeguard ecosystem health and services for future
 423 generations (Foley et al., 2010; Coccoli et al., 2018). Therefore, the proposed approach
 424 can enhance the monitoring of biodiversity status and trends and support the identification
 425 of areas most vulnerable to human activities for use in conservation planning.

426 5 Conclusions

427 This study demonstrates that CV models such as YOLOv8x and Faster R-CNN can
 428 successfully identify multiple benthic taxa in ROV imagery with performance levels
 429 comparable to or exceeding those reported in previous works. Moreover, it represents the
 430 first effort to model 13 benthic species in the south-eastern coast of the Bay of Biscay
 431 using an automatic computer-vision-based approach, highlighting the novelty and
 432 regional relevance of the approach. The results show that the models effectively detect
 433 most target classes, with the exception for taxa with strong morphological similarity (e.g.,
 434 *Geodia* spp. and sponges). Although the method currently offers only a rough initial
 435 estimation of taxa abundance, minimal human supervision substantially can enhance
 436 precision while still requiring considerably less effort than fully manual video analysis.
 437 Additionally, the model can be readily adapted for additional tasks such as labelling new
 438 video datasets.

439 Overall, this work contributes to more scalable, non-invasive and economical tools for
 440 estimating taxa abundance and mapping benthic habitats, thereby supporting more
 441 informed policy-making and sustainable resource management. Future work should
 442 prioritise improved annotation strategies and the development of more balanced training
 443 datasets, particularly by expanding the dataset through the collection of additional video
 444 material. Continued improvement of these elements will be essential for the successful

445 deployment of automated image-analysis systems in long-term biodiversity monitoring
446 programmes.

447 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

448 **Igor Granado:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis,
449 Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft. **Ibon Galparsoro:**
450 Conceptualization, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. **Xabier**
451 **Lekunberri:** Resources, Writing - Review & Editing. **Inma Martin:** Data labelling. **Joxe**
452 **M. Garmendia:** Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Natalia Montero:** Writing
453 - Review & Editing. **Jose A. Fernandes-Salvador:** Conceptualization, Resources,
454 Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition.

455 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

456 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
457 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

458 **Data statement**

459 The data that support this study are available from the corresponding author, I.G., upon
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